

M edico-Legal Talk

Medico-Legal Issues in Clinical Dental Practice

Dr. Avinash Pundlikrao Kale

BDS, MDS, Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics
 Post Graduate Fellowship in Micro Dentistry, Implant Training, C. Journalism, LLB (Law and Medicine), LLM (Constitutional Law and Administrative Law)
 Dental Surgeon, Department of Orthodontics Dentofacial Orthopedics, Government Dental College & Hospital, Saint Georges Hospital premises, Near CST, Mumbai
 Ex-Joint Secretary, Mumbai District Committee, Maharashtra State Gazetted Officers' Federation, Ground floor, New Administrative Building, Opp. Mantralaya, Mumbai
 Legal Consultant, Office of the Dean, Government of Maharashtra's Dental College and Hospital, Mumbai
 Ex-Legal Consultant, Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, Nashik, Maharashtra
 Legal Consultant, Directorate of Medical Education and Research, Mumbai, Government of Maharashtra

Concept and Importance of Informed Consent in Clinical Dental Practice:

Herewith, I extend my sincere thanks to the Administrator, the **Editorial Board** and the **Publisher** for publishing my article in medico-legal column in **November-December-2023** issue of this esteemed "**Heal Talk**" **Journal of Clinical Dentistry**. Also I extend my **Best Wishes** for **New Year-2024**, to the Administrator, the Editorial Board, the Publisher and valuable readers of this journal. I am happy to write and forward a next column on the importance of informed consent, subject of Medico-Legal issues in Clinical Dental Practice.

Introduction:

In first article (**Heal Talk // Nov-Dec 2023 // Vol-16 // No-2 // Issue-92, Pg No-14-15**) of this medico-legal column, readers have seen in brief, general idea about introduction of medico-legal issues. Wherein readers have seen: What is law and health? What is law and medicine? The article has also touched the terminologies like consent, names of various laws, rules, regulations, guidelines which governs medico-legal issues in Clinical Dental Practice.

In addition to general information about medico-issues, it is must to know for each dental practitioner some specific terminologies and their importance in Clinical Dental practice. In this current medico-legal article readers will get brief, general idea specifically on the concept and importance of Consent in day to day Clinical Dental practice. Amongst those laws which mentioned in earlier article, most prominent laws of land like Indian Constitution, Dentist Act of 1948, The Consumer Protection Act-1986 and many other adjunctive/supplementary Acts, Rules, Regulations and Guidelines laid down by judicial pronouncement has given birth to Rights and Duties to the patients and Dentists. Specifically the Indian Constitution has given 'Fundamental Rights' to Citizens of India.

The concept of "Doctrine of informed consent and patients' right of Self Determination":

The Apex Courts through various Landmark

judgments has explained these Fundamental Rights very elaborately and touched many aspects of human life. The right of health of citizen is not exception to it. The patient empowerment took place through the "Doctrine of informed consent and patients' right of Self Determination". Whenever the Dentist is performing his duty of treating any patients in his Clinical Dental Practice, it is an obligatory for the Dentist that, along with his duty of doing consented treatment, the Rights of patients must be protected. The Dentist must be very careful and vigilant that at any cost "No any rights of patient should be violated".

Justice Cardozo in case of *Schloendorff Vs Society of New York Hospital* (1914) held that a Surgeon who gives Medical and/or Surgical treatment or performs an operation without his patients consent, commits an assault on his patient for which he is liable for damages. In *Malette Vs Shulman et al* 1980, His Lordship Allen laid down the principle that doctor who proceeds to disregard the requirement of obtaining consent, is strictly liable for any untoward consequences resulting from the procedure of treatment, even if he conforms to the accepted medical practice. The concept of informed consent is based on the premise that each individual has a right to make decisions concerning his health, disease and treatment. Hence, in a doctor-patient relationship it is the duty of a doctor to explain the procedure and complications to his patient. It is the right of the patient to accept or reject the treatment.

Success of Dental Treatment:

As a Dentist all of us are well aware that, in the dentistry, the ultimate success of any treatment is mainly depends on, conducting careful, thorough evaluation of patient history, evaluating clinical findings for arriving at correct diagnosis. All kinds of dental clinical examinations, including all dental treatment procedures; whether preventive, interceptive, corrective or surgical involves interference with the human body. Every human being of adult years and sound mind has right to determine that, what should be done to his or her body. Hence as per humans right, before interference with patients body, patients consent is mandatory in eyes of law.

Definition of Consent: U/Sect-13 of the Indian Contract Act-1872:

The term consent, is said to have been given when two or more persons have agreed upon the same thing in the same sense. Thus, a consent postulates unity or mutuality of minds of the contracting parties.

The Consent is also defined as a free and voluntary agreement or approval or permission for compliance of some act between two or more persons. Doctor-patients' relationship is also based on same principle. Patient needs treatment and hence he comes to the doctor and doctor being professional will give the treatment. It is a contractual relationship.

Types of Consent:

Depending on patient's mode of expression, like from his just action or by expressing in words, the consent can be:

1. Implied consent,
2. Expressed Consent,
3. Informed Consent
4. Legally valid and invalid consent.

1. Implied consent:

When the conduct/action of the person/patient is clearly indicates that, he is agreeable to some act or he desires the act to be done on him. In that case it is implied that he has given implied consent. When a patient comes to the Dental practitioner, he does not expressly say that he needs treatment. But, as the patient entered in the dental clinic and seats in dental chair and opens his mouth, in which the dental treatment is provided by the Dentist to the patients. This conduct of the patients is

nothing but implied consent of the patients. However such implied consent of the patient is limited to the extent of preliminary procedures, such as history taking and clinical examinations for establishing diagnosis.

But it requires specific consent for the particular treatment procedures like complicated dental treatment procedures of extractions (Eg: Impacted teeth, Ankylosed teeth, Third molars, Badly carious root canal treated brittle teeth, Teeth with dilacerated roots and so on...) where the comparative probability of risk involved than normal extraction is high. Re-root canal treatment, Orthodontic treatment, implants and likewise any other procedures where the probability of risk involved is higher than routine dental treatment procedure. Thus for any specific treatment procedures apart from routine history taking and clinical examinations the Dentist must take definite consent from the patient by explaining the entire treatment procedures involved, prognosis of the treatment and complications likely to occurs during and post treatment.

In such cases after informing the patient, he is free to take decision of treatment acceptance or denial partially or in toto. That is right of self determination of the patients. In India the right of self determination flows from the right to health given under Article-21 of the Indian constitution.

2. Express consent: It can be verbal or written.

- a) **Verbal consent:** When consent is expressed verbally in words, it is verbal consent and
- b) **Written consent:** When consent is expressed in writing and signed by patient and witnessed by some other person. Where there is illiterate patient and he or she can not write, his mark or thumb print impression should be taken.

While drafting the written consent, the consent words should be clear, visible, without twisting of any words and without any ambiguity. So that later on while claiming, the patient can not deny the particular procedure whether diagnostic or therapeutic or surgical was done without his will or consent.

3. Informed consent: The foundation of the doctrine of informed consent is, "A conscious adult patient of sound mind is entitled to decide for himself or herself, whether or not, he will submit himself to a particular examination, a course of investigation or treatment proposed by the doctor, after the full disclosure of the nature and consequences about the investigation and the treatment."

4. Legally valid and invalid consent:

Section 14-22 of the Indian Contract Act 1872 defines the validity of consent. The Dentist must be aware about the validity of the consent in legal aspect. The consent given by the patient should be free from coercion, undue influence, fraud, misrepresentation or mistake. The Doctor/Dentist patient relationship is legally recognized as contractual relationship. Hence the basic foundation lies in consent and contract emerging out of it.

Ingredients of consent:

- i. Consent by adult age above 18 years age,
- ii. Consent with sound mind,
- iii. Consent with free will,
- iv. Consent must be for performing legal act as per concerned laws.

Who can give consent?:

- i. Adult age above 18 years,
- ii. Mentally sound person who is capable of understanding what he is doing or what is done to him.
- iii. Parents of child, close relatives or guardian, attendant and custodian of the patient for minor.
- iv. In some cases from the Court.

What are exceptions for consent? In emergency life threatening operation or condition, in situations like mass disaster:

In situations like in emergency life threatening operation or condition, mass disaster episodes, the treatment can be given without the informed consent as there is question of danger to his life. When accused patients is in police custody and he refuses for medical examination which is compulsory to prove or disprove an offence. In such instances the law allows the use of necessary force at the request of Police Officer (Not below the rank of Sub-inspector) to examine him without his consent or even if he refuses his consent for medical examination. Even a person who is on Bail can forcefully be examined by medical practitioner, if it is necessary for the action in law.

“Ignorance of law can not be excuse”:

Though the health profession has long been considered a noble profession. However in recent times, the patient doctor relationship has undergone major transformation. It is obligatory for the Dentist that he must be aware about the laws and rules related to their

profession like the consent laws. It is mandatory for the Dentist to explain the patient treatment procedures, risk involved, prognosis, alternative treatment approach and obtain legally valid consent in the eyes of law. Means the consent obtained should be from adult of sound mind, having age above 18 years and for legally valid treatment. Any consent obtained for illegal act, investigation or treatment procedure is not valid. For example the consent obtained for investigation of sex determination, the Medical Termination of Pregnancy (MTP) beyond the guidelines given in the concern law. The Dentist cannot take stand for his defense by saying that he was not aware about consent and taking legally valid consent before treatment is mandatory.

Do's and Don't:

1. Do not rely on blanket consent for one and all treatment procedure. Please take consent specifically and cautiously for the procedure to be done.
2. Do not obtain consent from patient fraudulently or by misrepresenting himself as a expert person to offer required treatment.
3. Explain the treatment procedures to the patient. Also inform about probable risk of procedures to be carried out. Also give options to the patient for alternative treatment available. While explaining this to patient use simple non technical language known to patient by choosing clear and unambiguous words.

Conclusion:

As all kinds of Dental treatment requires interference with the human body and every human being of adult age and sound mind has right to determine, what should be done to his body. Hence if the Dentist who gives any treatment or performs any operation on patients body without explaining him investigations, mode of treatment or surgical procedure, full disclosure of the nature, consequences, prognosis and risk involved in the treatment and also alternative mode of treatment and gives treatment without obtaining patient's informed consent. Then the Dentist commits an assault on his patient for which the Dentist is liable for damages. Hence, it is must to give all the above information to the patient in his or language and obtain informed consent from the patient before giving any treatment. If the Dentist fails to do this, then the act of the Dentist is considered as negligence in the eyes of law and is punishable in accordance with governing laws.